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**Polymeric Metal Complexes of
5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol**

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THIS communication is in continuation of the previous work on metallated complexes of 5,5'-(benzidinebisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline¹, and is a part of work on polymeric metal complexes being carried out in our laboratories¹⁻⁶. The synthesis and characterization of the insoluble pigments derived from 5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol (abbr. PDQO) are now being reported.

Experimental

The synthesis of 5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol was carried out by tetraazotizing 0.1 mol (10.8 g) of *p*-phenylenediamine and coupling the tetraazonium salt with 0.2 mol (29.0 g) of 8-quinolinol in pyridine medium as reported earlier⁷.

Mixtures of 0.01 mol metal acetate hydrate [ammonium iron(II) sulphate in the case of Fe(II)] and 0.01 mol the above bisazo dye (4.20 g) were refluxed in DMSO for 6 hr to obtain the metallated complexes, which were filtered, washed with hot DMSO and dried as usual. The complexes were amorphous dark brown solids, insoluble in water and in the usual organic solvents.

The estimation of C, H, N and the metal, as well as spectral and thermal studies were done as described in an earlier communication¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) reveal a metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1 as expected for a chain polymer, and the coordination of 2 H₂O per metal ion is inferred⁸. The ir spectra of the complexes of PDQO (Table 2) resemble closely those of the previously reported complexes of 5,5'-(benzidinebisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline^{1,8}.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF POLYMERIC PIGMENTS OF PDQO

Empirical formula	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
MnC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	56.39 (56.58)	3.63 (3.53)	16.15 (16.50)	10.62 (10.82)
FeC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	56.27 (56.48)	3.69 (3.52)	16.42 (16.49)	10.71 (10.96)
ZnC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	55.19 (55.48)	3.56 (3.48)	16.11 (16.18)	12.40 (12.52)
CdC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	50.45 (50.88)	3.27 (3.18)	14.64 (14.84)	19.55 (19.89)

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENT OF IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)

PDQO	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)	Assignment
—	3400- 3850	3400- 3850	3400- 3850	3400- 3360	^v OH(H ₂ O)
3380- 3120	—	—	—	—	^v OH
—	1640	1640	1630	1630	^δ OH(H ₂ O)
1600	1590	1590	1595	1595	^v C=N
1440	—	—	—	—	^δ OH
1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	^v C-O(O-O-M)
780	780	780	780	780	^v M-OH ₂
625	625	625	625	625	^v M-O
460	460	460	460	460	^v M-N

The electronic spectrum of the bisazo dye exhibits a band at 500 nm whose high intensity and wavelength suggest a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition attributed to the extensive conjugation resulting in lowering of the π^* orbital energy⁹. The *d-d* transition bands appear as weak shoulders on the intraligand band. The position and assignment of these bands are given in Table 3. Octahedral geometry around the

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF Mn(II) AND Fe(II) PIGMENTS

Metal	Band (nm)	Assignment	Geometry
Mn(II)	580	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (G)	Octahedral
	490	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (G)	
	440	→ ⁴ A _{1g} (G)	
	380	→ ⁶ E _g (G)	
	350	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (D)	
	330	→ ⁶ E _g (D)	
Fe(II)	720	⁶ B _{1g} → ⁶ B _{1g}	Octahedral

central metal is assigned¹⁰, which is in accordance with that previously reported for Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes⁹. In Fe(II) complex of lower symmetry, the E_g and T_{2g} states further split into A_{1g}, B_{1g} and B_{2g}, E_g.

Doubling of band is anticipated. It is assumed that the ground state is B_{2g} for these complexes, then ⁶B_{2g} → ⁶B_{1g} is 10D_q¹¹.

The modes of decomposition of these pigments resemble those of the previously reported complexes^{1,8}. The chelates begin to lose weight at an accelerated rate between 300-380° (Table 4). The

TABLE 4—TGA DATA OF COMPLEXES

Temp. °C	% Weight loss of pigment containing			
	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)
100	0.19	...	7.10	4.94
120	0.65	...	8.68	5.35
160	1.57	...	10.52	8.65
200	2.68	...	13.15	9.67
240	4.79	...	14.73	12.92
280	8.63	15.87	17.89	16.06
300	12.86	20.87	21.02	18.27
320	20.92	22.22	23.68	22.58
340	24.76	25.00	25.52	24.88
360	26.10	29.16	27.63	26.23
380	27.44	32.40	28.94	27.89
400	28.21	32.40	30.26	29.45
500	33.20	41.60	56.57	47.81
600	41.91	48.14	85.52	61.72
700	47.79	56.94	86.02	78.49
800	53.74	58.33	85.52	78.49
900	60.07	...	...	78.49

weight loss at temperatures lower than this range lies between 20–26%. The order of thermal stability is Cd(380°) > Mn(320°) > Fe(300°) ~ Zn(300°). The weights of the residues do not conform to those of the metal oxides.

The insolubility of the pigments, composition, ir spectra and thermal stability are evidences of their polymeric structure, as given below.

M = Mn(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II);
n = degree of polymerization.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zinc(II)

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DIVALENT zinc ion has completely filled $3d^{10}$ non-bonding shell and hence usually forms four coordinated tetrahedral compounds utilizing $4s4p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding. If experimental conditions are favourable, the coordination number can be increased to five involving one $4d$ orbital¹⁻³. This communication describes the mixed ligand complexes of the type $M[Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L]$ and $Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L'$ where $M = K^+$, Na^+ or Me_4N^+ ; $\beta\text{-dik}$ = acetylacetonate or dibenzoylmethanate; $L = SCN^-$, N_3^- or CN^- and L' = imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives.

Experimental

The β -diketonates of Zn(II) were prepared by the usual method⁴. Their thiocyanate, cyanide and azide adducts were obtained by refluxing the solutions of β -diketonates of Zn(II) in methanol with methanolic solutions of potassium thiocyanate, cyanide or sodium azide in 1:1 molar ratio for 2 to 3 hr. The mixed ligand complexes separated out on cooling. The compound $K[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$ so formed was treated with tetramethyl ammonium chloride in methanol. The precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to get the mixed ligand complex $Me_4N[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$. The complexes of the type $Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L'$ were prepared by refluxing Zn(II) acetylacetonate with imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives in methanol for 30 min to 2 hr. Morpholine and 2-methyl imidazole adducts separated out after keeping the solution overnight whereas other compounds separated out after 3 days. All the compounds were suction filtered, washed several times with ethanol to ensure complete removal of the excess ligand, followed by other and dried *in vacuo*.

The composition of the complexes was established by estimating zinc as $ZnNH_4PO_4$, sulphur as $BaSO_4$ after oxidizing with bromine in carbontetrachloride solution and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method⁵. The conductance measurements were carried out with $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions in acetone, pyridine and methanol medium using Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The infrared absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mull using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The physical, analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Results and Discussion

For the compounds of the type $M[Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L]$, the molar conductance data indicate them to be